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Role of E-banking Service Quality and its influence on Internet Banking Usage to E-Satisfaction Relationship with E-Loyalty

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Abstract

Purpose: This study intends to investigate the effects of e-banking service quality on e-banking satisfaction via a mediating effect of e-banking loyalty. During COVID-19, account holders of India's nationalized banks were polled to assess the electronic services offered by these institutions.

Design/ Methodology/Approach: The information was gathered using a customized questionnaire and 160 responses were included in the study. The data was statistically examined using SPSS and JAMOVI for structural equation modeling. The data show that e-banking loyalty is boosted by reliability and website design, especially during COVID-19.

Findings: The relationship between e-banking privacy and security and e-banking loyalty was shown to be totally mediated by e-banking satisfaction; however, the indirect influence of website design and dependability on e-banking loyalty was found to be partially mediated.

Practical implications: E-banking has evolved into one of the most important banking services that, when effectively implemented, may improve customer happiness while also providing banks with a competitive advantage. Knowing the relative relevance of several e-service quality characteristics can assist the banking business in focusing on client e-satisfaction.

Originality/Value: the effect of e-banking service quality, satisfaction between privacy & security and e-banking loyalty implies that customer give more importance because of privacy. In the event of future epidemics or natural disasters, consumers may exhibit similar behaviour to that seen during COVID-19's lockdown and social isolation. The researchers to understand the COVID – 19 and e-banking perspective in India.

Keywords: E-banking; E-service quality; E-satisfaction; E-loyalty; JAMOVI

1. Introduction

The rapid modernization of information technology and increasing competition in the financial sector has changed the landscape of the financial industry in recent decades (Koksal, 2016; Lee and Chung, 2009; Leung and Matanda, 2013; Mortimer, Neale, Hasan, and Dunphy, 2015; Rajeswari, Srinivasalu and Thiyagarajan, 2017). Technology has succeeded in making various aspects of life easier for the societies of today (Rust and Oliver, 1994). The development of a technology-based system has given businesses a whole new way to engage with their customers. The service business, specifically the banking industry, has undergone a massive transformation as a result of this innovation in how they communicate with their consumers. The advancement of information and communication technology (ICT) has altered the way businesses are

conducted. In information and business processes, technology serves as a link. Banks, like other businesses, have long benefited from information technology. ICT is being used in nearly every industry, such as business (Versteeg and Bouwman, 2006; Yi and Thomas, 2007), marketing (Qirici et al., 2011; Vilaseca-Requena et al., 2007), entrepreneurship (Malik et al., 2020), and so on. Every day, we observe changes in banking systems, and traditional banking is being phased out. In today's world, account holders always favour digital banking (Singh et al., 2017). It is crucial to note that customer experience is always a major issue for businesses (Mansoor et al., 2020). One of the unpredictable scenarios that helped customers, employees, and the general public understand shifts in business models was a recent pandemic (COVID-19) (Seetharaman, 2020). During the epidemic, banks witnessed a shift in consumer behaviour toward digital or electronic banking (Baldwin and Mauro, 2020; Wojcik & Ioannou, 2020). There were allegations of virus propagation via currency notes, which became a major motivator for people to switch to e-banking (Auer et al., 2020; Siva Kumar et al., 2020).

Most developed countries' banking industries were early adopters of e-services and have been actively involved in their development. The goal was to try to accommodate current clientele' ever-changing wants and lifestyles. The Indian banking sector, which is at the heart of the Indian economy, has seen remarkable growth, particularly in terms of electronic services (Fakhoury & Aubert, 2015). In the last few years, bank clients have increased their use of E-Banking services by roughly 25% to 30%. Indeed, Indian banks are strategically utilising advances in E-Banking services to retain and attract clients, and are investing heavily in implementing the most up-to-date E-Banking tactics in order to preserve and argue their competitive advantage. The cornerstone of banking services is built on consumer and bank trust, with the ultimate goal of providing high-quality services at low transaction costs (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019). In electronic surroundings, trust and loyalty are extremely important (Chaudhry et al., 2009). This value grows substantially in a pandemic crisis, as ICT is aimed at not only new advances but also consumer retention. This posed a difficulty for the banking industry as well, particularly in less developed nations, and the importance of knowledge management in commercial banks grew (Khokhar et al., 2010). Similarly quality of services was also termed as important in not only banking also in other industries, e.g. restaurants (Malik et al., 2020; Malik et al., 2013; Safi & Awan, 2018), life insurance (Ramamoorthy et al., 2016); Construction (Al-Momani, 2000; Love et al., 2000), etc.

The COVID-19 has altered people's lifestyles, interactions, and purchasing habits. COVID-19 is a life-threatening virus for people all around the world (Mamun and Ullah, 2020). Students are barred from taking classes online these days (Basilaia and Kvavadze, 2020), professors and officials are required to hold online meetings (Basilaia et al., 2020; Sahu, 2020), and buyers and sellers are focusing on electronic means as well (Hall et al., 2020; Rovetta and Bhagavathula, 2020). Digital means are becoming increasingly popular in the banking sector, where account holders are already heavily reliant on internet banking. Unpredictable, where COVID-19 has forced the closure of businesses around the world and pushed a large number of people into poverty, ample opportunities have arisen, such as in the field of information technology businesses, telehealth care and security firms. During the COVID-19, traditional banking deteriorated, resulting in a growth in e-banking platforms. As a result, the empirical capability to evaluate financial services is required to comprehend behavioural alterations. In India, too, there has been a considerable increase in e-banking activities during epidemic times. Electronic banking established a smooth flow of services with lower operational and fixed expenses and higher security features. People in India are more inclined to conduct their financial transactions online because they are not permitted to visit their bank branch. The study argument revolves around the solutions to research issues, which primarily concern how service quality and its dimensions are linked to e-satisfaction and e-loyalty in the banking system, as well as how e-satisfaction mediates these relationships.

This study heavily supported the emerging concept of different e-banking services quality (EBSQ) characteristics under COVID-19 as compared to normal conditions. This study is organized as follows: The following section will present a through “Literature Review”, followed by the “Method” and “Findings” of the study. An “Interpretation and Discussion” section analyzes the findings and provides implications as appropriate. Finally, the “Conclusion” section summarizes the study and presents pertinent limitations and recommendations for future research.

2. Literature Review

In India many studies have been conducted on the services quality of electronic banking. Thus almost few studies are available on this subject in India.

2.1 Theoretical Background

This study is theoretically backed by cognitive-motivational-relational theory as it connects the process of analyzing different perspectives and emotional responses of human toward evaluation (Kemper, 1992; Lazarus, 1993; Lazarus and Lazarus, 1991). Emotion stimulates practically all of the key events in our lives, and how we respond to them effects us as well (Kemper, 1992; Mansoor et al., 2020). The occurrence of cognitive orientation such as values, beliefs, and personal ambitions was determined by demographic traits, which resulted in a major reaction toward an event inside an environment (Shankar and Jebarajakirathy, 2019). The cognitive-motivational-relational theory has been utilized to relate the mechanism of characteristics of individual response and service quality in a number of studies. COVID-19, on the other hand, makes a different contribution to the cognitive-motivational-relational theory literature. Customers' loyalty in e-banking is elucidated by their response to the environment or an event, which can be considered an addition to the theoretical components.

2.1.1 E-Banking

Historically, the introduction of the first Automated Teller Machine (ATM) in Finland signaled the beginning of a new banking channel, propelling Finland to the forefront of E-Banking before it was widely adopted in other industrialized and developing countries (H.Sharma, 2011). E-Banking, or the distribution of financial services via electronic networks, has recently gained popularity among customers as a result of rapid advancements in technology and increased competition among banks (Mahadi, Rezaul, and Rahman, 2010).

E-banking services are defined by Lustsik (2004) as a variety of e-channels for conducting banking transactions via the Internet, telephone, television, mobile phone, and computer. As technology evolves and improves, banking clients' desires and expectations in terms of service grow. These days, the client wants to be able to operate and conduct banking transactions without having to go to the bank, at any time without being bound by the bank's operating hours, and to complete all of his or her payments (purchases, bills, and stocks) in a timely and cost-effective manner. As a result, the quality of financial services should be defined by independence, elasticity, freedom, and flexibility in order to meet these needs (Khalfan and Alshawaf, 2004).

2.1.2 E- Banking Service Quality and E-banking satisfaction

The majority of studies agree that service quality is a key metric for determining customer happiness (Abdul Kadir, 2011). Service quality has a clear positive impact on financial performance and has a considerable impact on customer satisfaction (Ming, 2003), as well as the financial performance of the organisation (Ashiqullah, 2006). As a result, the financial sector must change its focus to e-service quality in order to please and keep clients in the e-commerce environment. The relationship between the EBSQ and pleasure is still a hot topic in academia (Esengun et al, 2006; Haider et al., 2014). Some researchers suggested that the EBSQ is an antecedent of e-banking customer satisfaction, whereas others disagreed (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019). Earlier research referred to satisfaction as a predictor of service quality (Cronin et al., 2000; Cronin and Taylor, 1992; Dick and Basu, 1994; Parasuraman et al., 1985) Even if service quality is now read as electronic service quality, and the digital aspect is equally linked to satisfaction and loyalty, the conclusions of these classic studies cannot be ignored. According to an empirical study of customer perceptions of service quality in US banks, higher EBSQ quality leads to satisfaction (Foroughi et al., 2019). Website qualities, without a doubt, have an important part in increasing customer satisfaction (Amin, 2016; Roy et al., 2012), however different features leave varied impressions on consumers' thoughts (Bressolles et al., 2014). This vividly demonstrated the relationship between website design and e-banking customer satisfaction because the technicality of services affects customer happiness, support services supplied during e-banking should be less technical (Black et al., 2014). One of the most difficult aspects of using the internet as a service quality channel is determining how to manage e-service quality, which is critical to customer happiness (Ho and Wu, 1999). In order to maintain growth and market share in an e-commerce environment, internet enterprises must learn how to delight their clients. Customer satisfaction surveys have become standard practice in many financial organisations. As a result, the increasing desire for long-term profitability of dotcom enterprises and traditional companies that are net-enabled has highlighted a fundamental understanding of elements that determine web-customer happiness (Pathher et al., 2003). The service providers especially in e-banking are strictly advised to ensure focus on high level of secure information, confidentiality and transaction privacy (Brun et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2015). Significant impact of EBSQ on customer satisfaction in e-banking is also reported in this context

(Kassim and Abdullah, 2010). Hence, below hypothesis are formulated to empirically test in e-banking during COVID-19.

H1: Reliability in e-banking services positively influences e-banking satisfaction

H2: Privacy and Security in e-banking services positively influence e-banking satisfaction

H3: Website design in e-banking services positively influences e-banking satisfaction

H4: Customer service and support in e-banking services positively influence e-banking satisfaction.

2.1.3 E-banking service quality and E-loyalty

Customer loyalty is essential for any company organisation (Bhat et al., 2018), even if it is a significant barrier for a service firm to develop and maintain loyal clients (Mainardes et al., 2020). Loyalty is a multifaceted phenomenon with multiple qualities (Zeithaml et al., 1996). Customer loyalty is defined as a customer's evolving behavioural activity, which is followed by recurring purchasing behaviours (Fida et al., 2020). Consumer retention is a difficult process that is critical to a company's success (Bowen & Chen McCain, 2015). Consumers that are loyal to a provider are less susceptible to pricing changes and encourage future customers to use their services by promoting favourable word of mouth (Akbar and Parvez, 2009). As a result, a company's loyal customers are seen as a valuable asset. Customer loyalty in the context of e-banking can be characterised as "consumer predisposition to visit the bank's website frequently, routinely use e-banking services, and disseminate positive word of mouth about e-banking services" (Jeong and Lee, 2010; Kaur et al., 2012; Amin, 2016). EBSQ has four dimensions: reliability, privacy and security, website design and customer service, and e-banking support. The first factor, e-banking reliability, is critical since customer responsiveness is vital. Although reliability is one of the aspects that can influence answers, quick processing of banking transactions with zero errors is frequently used as a criterion for evaluating the reality of e-banking service providers (Blut et al., 2014; Liang and Pei-Ching, 2015; Saccani et al., 2014). The second dimension, privacy and security express the extent to which an e-banking user confidently shares personal information on an e-banking platform (Muturi et al., 2013). However, the trust element shifted toward service providers, and trust can help achieve the ideal consumer satisfaction response (Safi and Awan, 2018). Higher loyalty is a result of a better code of conduct for privacy and safety (Orel & Kara, 2014; Thaichon et al., 2014). The third dimension of EBSQ is website design, which is defined as numerous interactive aspects of the e-

banking service that help give consumers with transaction structure during and after processing, as well as more (Wolfenbarger and Gilly, 2003). An updated website (Kim et al., 2009) and improved interactive experience can result in a higher degree of satisfaction. The fourth dimension, customer service and support can be explained as the rapidity of retort toward any delinquent reported by user during or after service experience. The users here can be referred as both individuals and organizations (Blut et al., 2014). The support provided by the banking professional are considered more secured and assured while any trouble is faced in India (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019). Resultantly, all four dimensions are hypothesized as follows for empirical testing.

H5: Reliability in e-banking services positively influences e-banking loyalty.

H6: Privacy and security in e-banking services positively influences e-banking loyalty.

H7: Website design in e-banking services positively influences e-banking loyalty.

H8: Customer service and support in e-banking services positively influences e-banking loyalty.

2.1.4 Mediating effects of e-banking satisfaction

In general, organisations seek for greater customer happiness as a basic component. Customer loyalty may undoubtedly be gained by providing them with increased levels of satisfaction. E-satisfaction leads to attitudinal loyalty, which has a favourable influence on behaviour. E-satisfaction in banking can lead to increased utilisation of banking services and increased e-loyalty opportunities (Giao et al., 2020; Suariedewi and Suprapti, 2020). Internet speed and connectivity have a significant impact on customer happiness and loyalty (Chaudhry et al., 2009). In recent literature, studies have explored the strong association between e-satisfaction and e-loyalty; however, in the context of the pandemic, there has been little research on the influence of e-banking satisfaction and loyalty.

H9: E-banking satisfaction positively influences e-banking loyalty.

3. The proposed Conceptual Model

Based on the aforementioned literature review and the hypothesized relationships, a conceptual model has been developed for this study, which is illustrated in Figure 1. This model shows previously discussed hypotheses.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

4. Research Method

Figure 1 depicts the conceptual framework that was used in this study. The model is built with components from the e-banking service quality model. This study looks at how e-banking service quality and satisfaction affect e-banking loyalty in the context of the pandemic in India. Data was gathered from e-banking users via standardized surveys. The surveys were conducted entirely online. The online poll was delivered to e-banking users with randomly selected e-mail addresses gathered from banks and friends. A total of 250 online questionnaires were distributed, with 190 replies. After removing the invalid surveys, a total of 161 valid questionnaires were used to conduct the analysis.

4.1 Measures and Instrument Development

The scale was modified to accommodate e-banking in pandemic situations, with specific emphasis paid to ensuring that the meaning of constructs remained unchanged. There are two components to the survey questionnaire. The first segment is made up of things that are related to research constructs. Respondents were requested to submit demographic information in the second part.

The scales used to measure the study components were previously verified. However, where applicable, these scales were changed to fit the e-banking situation. Four items were used to measure reliability (Jayawardhena, 2004; Muturi et al., 2013; Ul Haq and Awan, 2020), three items were used to measure privacy and security (Ul Haq and Awan, 2020), four items were used

to measure website design (Jayawardhena, 2004), and five items were used to measure customer service and support (Jayawardhena, 2004). (Quach et al., 2016). Five and four items were used to measure e-banking satisfaction and e-banking loyalty, respectively (Amin, 2016). The items that operationalized all of the constructs were graded on a five-point Likert scale that ranged from strongly disagree(1) to strongly agree(5).

5. Data Analysis and Results

5.1 Demographics Analysis

The surveyed bank account holders had a larger ration of male (72.23%) as compared to female (27.77%). Most of them (699) were young adults, with an age range 18-27 years, which makes 71.61% of the total followed by 214 respondents with age range 28-37 years. The least (39) were in the age range 48-57 years. Education level: under graduate respondent was 39.4%, graduated respondent was 40.4% and 20.2% respondent were post graduates. Occupation; we used private sector in which 45.2% respondent was participated, 17.0% are from the public sector and self-employed were 23.4%. The monthly income ranged from a minimum of 30000 or lessor to 91000 or higher considering much variation in India. The respondents with a salary of 30000 or lesser encompassed around 45% of the total which shows that either they are working on low wage rate in the private sector. Least of them (13) fall under the income level ranging from 71000 to 80000. More than half of the respondents (58%) are working in private sector and least (1%) were self-employed in the sample. There was also a representation of students (274) in the sample. Most of the account holders (81.45%) frequently using e-banking platform and 94% of the account holders believed e-banking is more useful than conventional banking particularly because of lockdown restrictions, time and cost effectiveness. As they believed e-banking is useful for them and saves money and time too, trust showed on e-banking during COVID-19 is significant. The detailed demographic information of the sample is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demographic Category		No of Respondents (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	99	61.5
	Female	61	37.9
	Total	161	100
	18-27 years	154	95.7
	28-37 years	3	1.9

Age	37-47 years	1	0.6
	48-57 years	3	1.9
	Total	161	100
Marital Status	Married	154	95.7
	Unmarried	7	4.3
	Total	161	100
Educational Qualifications	SSLC & Higher secondary	5	3.1
	Diploma	47	29.2
	Graduate	87	54.0
	Post graduate	22	13.7
	Total	161	100
Occupation	Government employees	3	1.9
	Private Employees	6	3.7
	Self-Employed	5	3.1
	Students	147	91.3
	Total	161	100
Monthly Income	Less than 30000	149	92.5
	31,000 – 40000	4	2.5
	41000 - 50,000	1	.6
	51,000 – 60000	-	-
	Above 60000	7	4.3
	Total	161	100
E-banking Usage Frequency	Frequent User	65	40.4
	Not a Frequent User	96	59.6
	Total	161	100
E-banking Usefulness	Useful	127	78.9
	Not Useful	34	21.1
	Total	161	100
E-banking Cost and Timesaving	Yes	121	75.2
	No	40	24.8
	Total	161	100

Source: Primary Data

5.2 Measurement Model

Prior to applying the structural equation model (SEM), it is required to test the measurement model to observe the appropriateness of the latent variables (Ramamoorthy et. al, 2016). The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) indicates the competence of the measurement model with five fir indices, namely chi-square statistic, normed chi-square, comparative fir index (CFI), Tucker - Lewis Index (TLI) and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA). For the appropriateness of the model fir, normed chi-square value should be less than 5, NFI and TLI values should be above 0.9 and RMSEA should be less than 0.088 (Hair et al., 2010; Byrne, 2010). Based on the CFA tests, all six dimensions had adequate model-to-data fit: normed chi square value was 1.548 (below 5.0); CFI and TLI were 0.956 and 0.947, respectively (above 0.9); and RMSEA value was 0.055 (less than 0.088). Tucker - Lewis Index (TLI) result of .947 is considerably above the .95 threshold denoting satisfactory model fit.

This study to ensure the reliability and validity among constructs, measurement analysis recommended (Hair et al., 2010). Convergent and discriminant validity were examined through factor loadings, average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (CR) values (Cheah et al., 2018). The cutoff point for each measure varies, factors loading value must be greater or equal to 0.70 or 0.50, and Cronbach's alpha and CR values falling between 0.60 and 0.70 are acceptable (Hair et al., 2010). The acceptable AVE values should be 0.50 or greater (Cheah et al., 2018) by comparing diagonal values with the correlation coefficients for each construct in the relevant rows and columns (Hair et al., 2010). Table 2 depicts that all the values are in range, except three items which were deleted because of lower factor loadings and further analysis was performed. The values of all constructs indicated good validity, consistency and accuracy of the measurement model.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Table 2. Cronbach's alpha, AVE and CR values

Variable	Item	Composite reliability (CR)	AVE
Reliability	REL1	0.716	0.57
	REL2		
	REL3		
	REL4		
Privacy and Security	P&S1	0.850	0.74
	P&S2		
	P&S3		
	WD1	0.841	0.72
	WD2		

Website Design	WD3		
	WD4		
	WD5		
Customer service and support	CSS1	0.846	0.51
	CSS2		
	CSS3		
	CSS4		
	CSS5		
E-banking satisfaction	EBS1	0.819	0.87
	EBS2		
	EBS3		
	EBS4		
E-banking loyalty	EBL1	0.789	0.81
	EBL2		
	EBL3		
	EBL4		

5.3 Structural Model Assessment

The present study used structural equation modeling (SEM) to test the relationships between independent and dependent variables (Kline, 2011; Ramamoorthy et. al, 2016). The estimation of a structural model was established through path analysis. This study tested a structural model with hypotheses to estimate the relationships of e-banking service quality with e-banking satisfaction and e-loyalty of e-banking users (Figure 2). For the structural model (SEM) was performed using open source software JAMOVI. In the next step, the structural model related to dependent and independent variables was specified in order to test the hypotheses.

In this model, there were four exogenous variables (Reliability, privacy and security, web design, customer service and support, and two endogenous variables (e-banking satisfaction and e-banking loyalty). This model fit the data this model fit the data well as per the following standard model fit indicators: $\chi^2 = 388$, where $df = 256$ (<3 ; Kline, 1998; Gopinath et. al, 2020), goodness of fit index (GFI) = 0.98, CFI = 0.95, TLI = 0.94, NFI = 0.88, RMSEA = 0.05 (<0.08), and we checked standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) = 0.04 (<0.05).

Figure 3: Structural Model

Furthermore, the R-square values provide an indication of the predictive ability of the constructs of the model. E-banking satisfaction an R-square of 0.91 and E-banking loyalty an R-square of 0.63, thereby confirming the predictive ability of the model and all the hypotheses related to e-banking service quality in this research. The structural model appears in Figure 3.

The usually β , p – values and t-values are considered to accept or reject the hypothesis. Here, H1, H3 and H4 were accepted ($\beta = 0.078$, t-values = 3.218 and p-values = 0.001; $\beta = 0.08$, t-values = 3.363, p-value = 0.353 and $\beta = 0.079$, t- value = 3.231, p-value = 0.001) and H2 were rejected ($\beta = -0.049$, t-values = 1.819, p-value = 0.035) the results confirmed, three predictors (reliability, website design and customer service and support) influence negatively however (privacy and security) effect positively. The results of H5, H6 and H7, respectively, demonstrated $\beta = 0.121$, t-values = 3.052, p-value = 0.001, $\beta = 0.321$, t-values = 3.519, p-value = 0.000 and $\beta = 0.27$, t-values = 5.798, p – value = 0.000, reporting the positive influence of e-banking customer satisfaction on loyalty. In contrast, in H8 the negative effect on loyalty was reported ($\beta = -0.306$,

t – value = 4.113, p – value = 0.067). Finally, H9 with $\beta = 0.684$, t – value = 7.726, p – value = 0.000 confirmed the proposed hypothesis and significant positive impact was proved.

5.4 Discussion

This study was carried out not only to increase e-banking loyalty by leveraging and providing high-quality services in an e-banking environment, but also to examine account holders' behavioural changes during pandemic times. With minor exceptions, the findings are consistent with previous researchers (Chaudhry et al., 2009; Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019), most likely because to COVID-19's difficult time. The unimportance of the relationship between privacy and security and customer service and assistance was demonstrated, and mediation was not expected (Quach et al., 2016). The findings are new because, due to their busy schedules, individuals normally do not pay attention to website design; nonetheless, they are concerned about website design and reliability. Customer service and support must satisfy account holders, who will subsequently become a source of loyalty throughout COVID-19. As a result, the indirect influence of reliability and website design on EBL via EBS was shown to be slightly mediated, however full mediation was found for customer service and support.

Hypothesis Testing

	Hypothesis Relationship	t- value	p- value	Results
H1	R → EBL	3.218	0.001	Supported
H2	P & S → EBL	1.819	0.035	Not supported
H3	WD → EBL	3.363	0.353	Supported
H4	CSS → EBL	3.231	0.001	Supported
H5	R → EBS	3.052	0.001	Supported
H6	P & S → EBS	3.519	0.000	Supported
H7	WD → EBS	5.798	0.000	Supported
H8	CSS → EBL	4.113	0.067	Not supported
H9	EBL → EBS	7.726	0.000	Supported

People may not have found their difficulties entirely resolved by the customer service and support department during the epidemic because of the rejected indirect effect of customer service and support on e-banking loyalty via e-banking satisfaction. Customers will never be content or loyal unless and until their problems and concerns are handled; therefore, genuine care on the part of banks and other such institutions is required, particularly during difficult times

such as the Coronavirus pandemic. As a result, this study contributed to the advancement of the field and supported the use of EBSQ in these epidemic studies as well. During the pandemic, e-banking facilities and services should be supplied in a way that appeals customers while focusing on cost effectiveness. COVID-19.

6. Conclusion, Implications and Future research

The current circumstances have increased the demand for e-banking, had a significant impact on the use of traditional banking, and focused on the impact during the pandemic, but their preferences related to trust, safety and security, reliability, website designs, and customer service, which is an interesting departure from previous literature. The difficulty of the situation during the pandemic is most likely the reason (COVID-19).

This study emphasises the link between CMR and COVID-19, and so adds to the literature in a unique way. The banking industry can use the findings of this study to develop e-banking strategies, particularly in times of epidemics and natural disasters that will assist banks maintain existing account holders while also attracting new ones. Customers' perceptions and elements that make them more satisfied and loyal to e-banking services may also be understood by service providers. This study also provides insight into consumers' objectives and focuses, which are necessary of e-banking services in order for users to become loyal and content with online banking platforms throughout the shutdown. It also aids banks in making strategic decisions in order to better India's e-banking future.

This research was limited to Indian especially Telangana e-banking environment because of accessibility issue of respondents and time constraint as quick research is needed and appreciated in these unprecedented times. We have considered only the mediated impact of e-banking customer satisfaction moreover it was quite difficult for us to build a relationship between EBSQ dimensions with e-banking satisfaction because of relatively less literature in the similar context. Further research can empirically evaluate the relationship between initial trust and customer happiness in e-banking, using data from several districts across Telangana. A study that compares states to other states in India can be beneficial. Future studies should also examine combining strategic management theories to investigate the EBSQ link. To expand on this research, it is suggested that methods for improving the reliability of "E-Banking" services, particularly in India, be examined. Furthermore, the meaning of "reliability" may vary across

India, even within the region, necessitating a thorough examination of this and other constructs in various cultural settings.

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